

stakeholder

UMC Utrecht

netherlands

eScience center

Googling the Cancer Genome Project

Hartwig
MEDICAL FOUNDATION

time

DMP

DPIA

DTA

HPC

DPA

DMP

DPIA

DTA

DPA

From:
project members, data steward

To:
project members, partners, peers

From:
project members, data steward,
data protection officer

To:
project members, partners, peers

From:
data controller (**HMF**)

To:
data processor (**UMCU**)

From:
data controller (**UMCU**)

To:
data processor (**SURFsara**)

- Contains:**
- ownership, rights, responsibilities
 - workflows, processes, agreements for backing-up , storing, and sharing data
 - defined standards for data capturing, metadata creation, and documentation
 - decisions about processing, sharing, publishing, and archiving research output

- Contains:**
- Workflow of data flow and overview of infrastructure
 - Risk assessment and tailored advice
 - Risk assessment table

- Contains:**
- binding legal contract that enables the transfer of data according to a set of principles
 - data protection and data processing requirements for the data requesting party (the data processor)

- Contains:**
- binding legal contract that enables the processing of data on the super computer
 - data protection and data processing requirements for the data requesting party (the data processor)

Needed to give a signature:

Division manager from UMC Utrecht
Director of business development from SURFsara
GTCG project Principal Investigator

Contact details needed of:

Security officer of the division from the UMC Utrecht
Security officer from SURFsara
Data Protection Officer from UMC Utrecht
Security manager from SURFsara

Data Processing Agreement

From: data controller (UMCU)

To: data processor (SURFsara)

Outline of UMCU DPA template 2019:

1. Definitions of terms and regulations
2. Subject of this progressing agreement
3. Execution of processing
4. Security of personal data and control
5. Monitoring, information obligations and incident management
6. Cooperation obligations
7. Engaging sub processors
8. Liability
9. Duration and termination
10. Retention periods, return and destruction of personal data
11. Intellectual Property rights
12. Financial provisions

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Logos on Slide 1

UMC Utrecht Logo: <https://worldvectorlogo.com/logo/umc-utrecht-1>

eScience Center Logo: <https://www.esciencecenter.nl/>

Hartwig Medical Foundation Logo: <https://www.hartwigmedicalfoundation.nl/en/>

SURFsara logo: <https://userinfo.surfsara.nl/>